

**ISSUES OF ORGANIZING STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT WORK IN MODERN PHYSICS
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ABSTRACT

The article describes the issues of organizing the independent work of physics students in technical higher education institutions based on modern education. It was noted that organizing students' independent work based on modern educational requirements, developing students' creative abilities, and increasing their interest and desire to acquire new knowledge will help to improve the quality and efficiency of education. Examples of topics that can be given as independent work are given. Issues of organizing students' independent work were discussed in problem-solving and laboratory sessions.

Keywords: independent work, information technology, soliton, turbulence, clusters, fullerenes, reductive radiation, dark matter, dark energy.

INTRODUCTION

The reforms carried out in the education system are aimed at ensuring that the knowledge and skills of graduates of higher education institutions are at the level of modern requirements. Today's specialists are required to be fully mature with independent thinking, decision-making abilities, and active life positions, in addition to having deep and extensive knowledge and skills necessary for their practical professional activities. Formation of independent work skills in students is of great importance in the preparation of highly qualified personnel. In this regard, organizing students' independent work based on modern educational requirements, developing students' creative abilities, and increasing their interest and desire to acquire new knowledge plays an important role in improving the quality and efficiency of education.

MAIN PART

In the process of education, students should learn to acquire knowledge independently, because, for them, the knowledge obtained in this way is relatively stronger. Life experience and pedagogical observations show a lack of independent activity and work skills among elementary school students in recent years. On the other hand, for example, the volume of educational materials in physics has doubled, and the time required to study them has decreased by almost as much. In this regard, the time allotted for independent work of students has been increased. From this point of view, training students for independent activities and work, rational and correct organization of their independent work requires a serious and creative approach to this issue

from pedagogues. The analysis of pedagogical research shows that only properly organized active independent activity creates conditions and helps the development of the future specialist's personality and professional skills. Because when students do independent work, they are free in every way, they have the opportunity to choose a convenient time, situation, and necessary tools to complete the tasks and control their work. It is appropriate to pay attention to the following factors when organizing students' independent work. The independent work of the students should be carried out under the constant guidance of the teacher. It is necessary to ensure the availability of necessary teaching and methodical materials and opportunities for their use for independent work. These materials may be in written or electronic form. Effective use of information technologies is of great importance in organizing students' independent work. In modern physics education, the independent work of students remains an integral part of the educational process. Independent works organized in the field of physics are distinguished by some aspects. Because independent work should be conducted on all types of training, ie lectures, practical problem solving, and laboratory training.

Modern physics is developing very quickly, and the amount of scientific information and new knowledge to be acquired is increasing dramatically. On the contrary, coverage of science news in curricula and textbooks lags. In such conditions, the importance of independent work increases even more. In addition to the traditional topics included in the curriculum, when choosing topics for independent work in the lecture, for talented students who want to expand their knowledge, topics dedicated to modern problems and achievements of physics can be included in the list. Here are examples of topics that can be given as independent work.

- Wave processes in nonlinear media. Solitons.

The ninth value.

- Turbulence processes in different environments. in liquids, turbulent flows in the atmosphere, and solar plasma.

- Dynamic systems far from equilibrium. Eigenvalues in dissipative systems self-organizing phenomena.

- Cluster state of atoms. Carbon nanotubes. Fullerenes their practical application prospects.

- Semiconductor nanostructures. Quantum dots, threads, and coils.

- Quantum Hall effect. Integer and Fractional Hall Effect. Two-dimensional electronic systems.

- Macroscopic quantum effects. Extreme fluidity.

- Quantum informatics. Quantum computers. Quantum cryptography and

teleportation.

- Fundamental interactions. General field theory.
- Universe evolution. Big bang. The Expanding Universe Model.

Relective radiation.

- Stellar evolution. White dwarfs, neutron stars, and black holes
- Dark matter and dark energy
- The emergence of life and thinking is the modern science of physics interpretation based on imagination and others.

A lot of information on the subject can be found on the Internet. Students can prepare independent works in the form of an abstract or a scientific report and present these works at specially organized small scientific seminars or conferences.

These activities help students to develop scientific research skills. If the chosen topic covers a wide range of problems and issues, students can do independent work related to this topic as a team in small groups and submit it in the form of a presentation. In this case, independent work appears as a real creative activity. Because an interactive environment is created when doing work. As a result of the discussion, students will have the opportunity to openly express their point of view, to enrich each other with new information and knowledge through the means of mutual exchange of ideas.

In the problem-solving sessions, students are divided into independent work that they do in the classroom and at home. Problem-solving is the most effective way to strengthen theoretical knowledge. Therefore, student activity is important in problem-solving classes. Most students will be passive observers if the teacher or a good student solves the problem on the blackboard. To activate students, it is possible to use handout options, which are dedicated to the desired topic and consist of several questions prepared in advance for each student. To do this, the teacher will first give a brief description of the general instructions on the topic and solve several problems as examples. The rest of the time, independent work options are distributed to students. Students go into active work mode. The options should be composed of easier problems that students can solve and more difficult problems that require thinking and are intended for students who claim higher grades. As a result, the employment of students is ensured. They need to ask the teacher a question. The teacher directs and controls the independent work of students by answering questions. It is also possible to organize independent work outside of class.

If the situation and conditions are created for students to work more independently in the laboratory sessions, if they develop the ability to independently analyze and evaluate the results

and understand their scientific and practical significance, then the skills of independent application of the acquired knowledge to practice will be formed faster.

CONCLUSION

From the discussions described above, it can be concluded that organizing students' independent work based on modern educational requirements, developing students' creative abilities, forming their independent work skills, and gaining their interest and desire to acquire new knowledge is of great importance in improving the quality and efficiency of education.

Teaching students for independent activities and work, and organizing their independent work rationally and purposefully requires teachers to approach this issue creatively. It should be noted that only properly organized independent activities create conditions and help the development of the future specialist's personality and professional skills. Students' independent work should be carried out under the constant guidance of the teacher. Effective use of information technologies and resources is of great importance in organizing students' independent work. Independent work should be carried out on all types of training, namely lectures, practical problem solving, and laboratory training.

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